
Data Assimilation of realistic SWOT satellite observations

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ABSTRACT

For the past 25 years, satellite altimetry has produced Sea Surface Height (SSH) maps which have allowed oceanographers to study large-scale ocean dynamics ($> 200km$). However, the small scales of ocean circulation play a key role in a variety of natural phenomena.

In order to research on finer scale ocean dynamics, the future SWOT mission will provide the capability of making measurements of SSH with unprecedented resolution. This will bring challenges to the current data processing techniques and therefore, more advanced techniques are being developed. One such technique is the Back-and-Forth Nudging (BFN) data assimilation method which provides SSH maps consistent with both real-world measurements and the physics of a numerical ocean model. The objective of this project is to test and evaluate different strategies for implementing the BFN method with realistic SWOT observations accounting for both noise and errors.

The results show that, for a low signal-to-noise ratio region, de-noising the SWOT observations is essential for a good performance of BFN. Under de-noised observations, the best strategy was found to be by nudging only the relative vorticity (RV) term. This strategy reconstructed SSH fields with an effective resolution of 60 km and RMSE score of 0.81. For a region with high signal-to-noise ratio, the BFN method appeared robust to noisy observations. Once again, it was found that after de-noising observations, the best strategy was nudging the RV term only. This strategy reconstructed SSH fields with an effective resolution of 89.9 km and RMSE score of 0.86.

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1 Introduction

For the past 25 years, it has been possible to quantify and study large-scale ocean dynamics ($> 200km$) using measurements of Sea Surface Height (SSH) obtained by Nadir altimeter satellites. The measurement of SSH enables the computation of its derivatives and thus, of horizontal pressure gradients. This has enabled the description of the upper ocean dynamics based on geostrophy which is the state of the ocean for which the Coriolis force exactly balances the horizontal pressure gradient force. Based on local SSH measurements, maps of SSH can be derived and prove useful in the study of a variety of natural phenomena such as, ocean dynamics and their impact on the global climate (Morrow and Le Traon 2012).

The current effective resolution of SSH maps is of 150-200 km (Ballarotta et al. 2019) and is not enough to capture mesoscale and sub-mesoscale dynamics. Therefore, the scientific community is "blind" to the processes happening at these smaller scales and their local and global interactions with other systems. On the other hand, it has been suggested that these processes play a key role in a variety of physical phenomena related to the Earth's climate, the ocean's energy and carbon budgets, amongst others (Morrow et al. 2019).

In order to deepen the knowledge base on ocean dynamics, the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission is being developed. This mission entails a state-of-the-art satellite (namely the SWOT satellite) planned for launch in 2021. This satellite is expected to observe SSH at resolutions of 15-45 km (Wang et al. 2019) and, to exploit this new capability, more advanced data processing techniques are being developed.

An attractive technique to derive SSH maps from SWOT and Nadir measurements is Data Assimilation (DA). DA uses numerical models of the ocean to interpolate the SSH measurements in time and space. The resulting SSH maps are consistent with both the real-world measurements and the physics of the model. A specific DA method is the Back-and-Forth Nudging (BFN) algorithm proposed by Le Guillou et al. 2020. In Le Guillou et al. 2020, simulated SWOT and Nadir observations are fed into a quasi-geostrophic ocean model and the resulting SSH fields seem promising. However, the used SWOT observations are "perfect" i.e. without any account for SWOT measurement noise and errors. The objective of this paper is to test and evaluate the BFN algorithm with realistic SWOT observations accounting for both noise and errors.

The data provided by the SWOT satellite will be contaminated by small-scale random noise and spatially correlated errors. The random noise affects the magnitude of the SSH data in a random fashion making it impossible to retrieve SSH derivatives which are essential to reconstruct current fields. Therefore, the removal of this type of noise prior to the DA process is critical. The work of Gómez-Navarro et al. 2020 brought forth a SWOT-specific random noise filtering technique. This de-noising method effectively removes random noise from SWOT observations and thus, makes it possible to compute SSH derivatives.

As a first experiment in this research, the virgin, noisy SWOT observations will be fed to the BFN. Then, using the de-noising tool, SWOT observations will be de-noised prior to the BFN method. These experiments will be carried out for two distinct regions of the North Atlantic basin with contrasting dynamics and signal-to-noise ratios. The resulting reconstructed fields for both experiments will then be evaluated and compared.

The overall context and issues arising from this mission are put forward in Section 2. Then, in Section 3 the DA method, the ocean model under scope and the implementation of the algorithm are explained. In Section 4 the experimental set-up is clarified. And finally, the results, discussion and conclusions are put forward in Sections 5 and 6.

2 The SWOT satellite

2.1 State of the art: DUACS

At the moment, the most used SSH-derived products are the Developing Use of Altimetry for Climate Studies (DUACS) maps. These maps are created by a relatively simple statistical interpolation in space and time of Nadir satellite data (Dibarboure, Pujol, Briol, et al. 2011).

The resolution of DUACS maps is hindered by the current sensor technology - nadir altimeters measure 1D SSH profiles with a high along-track resolution of 7km but with large gaps between tracks that can reach 200km (Le Guillou et al. 2020). Additionally, it is not possible to observe along-track scales smaller than 50km due to noise. Therefore, the DUACS maps do not resolve scales smaller than 150km. However, given their daily global coverage these have become essential for oceanographic applications. Nevertheless, in order to obtain more insights into mesoscale and submesoscale ocean processes it is of essence to obtain SSH data with a much higher resolution.

2.2 The SWOT Mission

The SWOT mission is the fruit of the collaboration between North American and European oceanographers and hydrologists and other international partners. SWOT is being collectively developed by NASA and the Centre National D'Études Spatiales (CNES) with contributions from the Canadian Space Agency (CSA) and the United Kingdom Space Agency. This satellite mission has been developed to make the first global survey of Earth's surface water, observe the fine details of the ocean's surface topography, and measure how water bodies change over time (*NASA SWOT - Mission* 2020).

The SWOT mission will make unprecedented high-resolution 2D observations of SSH using SAR radar interferometric techniques (Figure 1). This mission is expected to fill the knowledge gap on the dynamics of ocean processes within the 15-150km scale. From an oceanographic perspective, the main objective of SWOT is to quantify ocean surface currents and vertical exchanges below the surface and thus, better understand the role of fine-scale surface processes in the global climate system (MEOM 2017).

2.3 Challenges to DUACS

The SWOT mission will be a disruptive project and will bring challenges to the current data interpolation method of DUACS. The main reasons are due to:

- **Resolution:** The current DUACS' processing method is not designed for high spatial resolution. Furthermore, the spatial and time resolutions of SWOT are incompatible making it very difficult to track submesoscale processes with the current, simple interpolation of DUACS. SWOT will have a typical revisit time of 10 days at mid-latitude, preventing the tracking of fine-scale processes with time scales of one or two days.
- **Noise:** The relatively low signal-to-noise ratio of SWOT will require the development of new and dedicated methods to filter out noise.
- **Amount of data:** The performance of the DUACS algorithm will be highly affected by the steep increase in the amount of data.

Figure 1: Left: Concept of the SWOT mission. A radar source positioned at an end of the baseline alternatively emits towards each swath. Both antennas receive the reflected signals. Ka-band Radar Interferometry (KaRIn) allows to recover SSH measurements at very high resolution. **Right:** Simulation of a SWOT pass over the Gulf Stream region. This simulation is based on a SSH field from the NATL60 North Atlantic simulation at $1/60^\circ$ resolution and the SWOT simulator (MEOM 2017).

The development of new algorithms to deal with SWOT data is therefore, essential for the success of the SWOT mission. It is no longer possible to simply interpolate the data between two measurements. The submesoscale dynamics are "faster" than the revisit time of the SWOT satellite. Luckily, it is known that High-resolution Numerical Ocean Circulation Models (NOCM) together with Data Assimilation (DA) methods have the potential to solve this and other issues that arise from the implementation of SWOT. In Section 3, the DA method and corresponding NOCM which concern this project will be discussed.

2.4 The SWOT Noise and its De-noising

The data provided by the SWOT satellite will be contaminated by small-scale random noise and spatially correlated errors. The SWOT errors considered in this research are shown in Figure 2. In this Figure strong long-range correlations can be seen for most error types, whereas the Ka-band Radar Interferometer (KaRIn) noise is effectively random.

As can be seen in Figure 2, the spatially correlated errors include satellite roll errors composed of the errors in the knowledge of the spacecraft roll angle and roll control; phase errors introduced by each antenna; baseline dilation errors due to the distortion of the baseline mast (see Figure 1); and the timing error corresponding to a common group delay error of the system. Finally, the random noise is an instrumental noise intrinsic to the KaRIn and is spatially uncorrelated. Further details about the SWOT noise and errors can be found in Esteban-Fernandez 2014 and details about their simulation by the SWOT simulator can be found in Gaultier, Ubelmann, et al. 2016.

The KaRIn noise affects the magnitude of the SSH data in a random fashion making it impossible to retrieve SSH derivatives. Hence, removing this noise from the SWOT

Figure 2: Examples of errors (m) added by the SWOT simulator to the GULFSTREAM region for pass 93 of cycle 01 of the satellite’s orbit and considering a space-time sampling typical of the Science Phase of the mission. In the center of the passes the 20 km Nadir gap can be seen.

observations is of extreme importance. The correct reconstruction of the derivatives enables the computation of physical variables such as the geostrophic velocity and vorticity. Additionally, DA methods, such as the one used in this paper, use the information on the derivatives to mitigate the effect of correlated errors ((Ruggiero, Cosme, Brankart, et al. 2016)).

A new de-noising technique for the SWOT data has been proposed by Gómez-Navarro et al. 2020 where the random small-scale KaRIn noise can be effectively removed. The de-noising model is formulated as a regularized least-square problem with a Tikhonov regularization based on the first-, second-, and third-order derivatives of SSH. This is the chosen method to de-noise SWOT observations in this research and details can be found in Section 4.1.

3 The Data Assimilation Method

3.1 Back and Forth Nudging Algorithm

The nudging technique is a data assimilation method that consists in adding a feedback term to the dynamical equation governing a model. In the presence of real-world observations for a given phenomenon, this term will “push” the model’s state towards the observed, real-world state. This so-called “nudging term” is proportional to the difference between the observation and the state of the model.

As an example, take the following dynamical model:

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial t} = M(X, t) \quad (1)$$

Where X is the state variable and M represents the physics of the model. Assuming that real-world observations, Y_{obs} , are available for a time window $[0, T]$ then the model’s state can be nudged towards the observations either forward or backward in time.

Given a known initial state x_0 , the forward nudging can be implemented by the following

system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial X}{\partial t} = M(X, t) + K(Y_{obs} - X) & \text{for } 0 \leq t \leq T, \\ X(0) = x_0. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

On the other hand, given a known final condition, x_T , and assuming a fully reversible model, the backward nudging can be implemented as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial X}{\partial t} = M(X, t) - K(Y_{obs} - X), & \text{for } T \geq t \geq 0, \\ X(T) = x_T. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

For both these systems, K is the nudging coefficient with the dimension of the inverse of time. K determines the extent to which the model's state is pushed towards the observations - the larger its value the stronger the "push" and the more influence the real-world observation will have.

The Back and Forth Nudging (BFN) algorithm is the combination of these two nudging techniques in an iterative process. This process starts by the forward nudging of the model given a known initial state. Then, the obtained final state is used as an initial state for the backward nudging. After several iterations this algorithm converges towards an optimal trajectory which best fits both the observations and the model's physics (Le Guillou et al. 2020).

In summary, in order to implement a BFN algorithm one needs (i) real-world observations of a given state of a system, (ii) a dynamical model that propagates the state of the system and (iii) a known initial state and boundary conditions. The specifics related to the implementation of the BFN technique in this research can be found in Section 4.

3.2 The Quasi-geostrophic equations

The Quasi-geostrophic (QG) model is a 1.5 layer ocean model that propagates SSH fields without considering mixing nor forcings. The dynamics are dictated by the conservation of Potential Vorticity (PV), q :

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + J(\psi, q) = 0 \quad (4)$$

where J is the jacobian operator and ψ is the streamfunction. This function is proportional to SSH as:

$$\psi = \frac{g}{f} SSH \quad (5)$$

where g is the gravitational constant and f the Coriolis parameter. Additionally, the PV relates to the streamfunction, ψ , as:

$$q = \nabla^2 \psi - \frac{1}{L_R^2} \psi \quad (6)$$

where L_R is the Rossby deformation radius. Equation 6 is composed of two terms. The first is the relative vorticity (RV), $\nabla^2 \psi$, which is the vorticity of the fluid as viewed from the rotating frame of the Earth and the second is the vortex stretching (VS), $\frac{1}{L_R^2} \psi$, which

describes the mechanisms of stretching of fluid columns. From here on these terms will be referred to as RV term and VS term, respectively.

3.3 Nudging operation and effects of noise

As can be seen from the presented QG equations, the prognostic variable is q , the potential vorticity (commonly referred to as PV). However, in the context of the SWOT mission SSH measurements are taken and thus, PV is not directly observable. This implies that the nudging operation will take observations of SSH but nudge the PV. Since PV is composed of two terms, three possible nudging strategies arise: nudging both terms and thus, nudging the full PV; nudging only the RV term or nudging only the VS term. The general form of the nudging term is:

$$K(Y_{obs} - X) = -\frac{1}{L_R^2} K_{SSH} \left(\frac{g}{f} SSH_{obs} - \psi \right) + K_{RV} \left[\nabla^2 \left(\frac{g}{f} SSH_{obs} \right) - \nabla^2 \psi \right] \quad (7)$$

where SSH_{obs} is the observed SSH , ψ is the streamfunction of the model, L_R the Rossby radius, g the gravitational constant and f the Coriolis parameter. K_{SSH} and K_{RV} are the nudging coefficients that set the strength of the nudging for each term. In this work, this operation is implemented using the same coefficients as in the work of Le Guillou et al. 2020.

As stated in Section 2.4, the SWOT random measurement noise has repercussions in the computations of derivatives. Therefore, in the presence of such noise it is not possible to perform the nudging operation on the RV term. The opposite happens for the case of spatially correlated SWOT errors. These errors affect mainly the VS term since they generate errors in the magnitude of the signal but not on its dynamics. Thus, under noisy SWOT observations different nudging strategies will yield different results and similarly under de-noised observations. In this work, the main objective is to study the different behaviours of the BFN algorithm under these types of observations.

4 Experimental set-up

Currently, the work of Le Guillou et al. 2020 uses the BFN technique together with a quasi-geostrophic (QG) model (as presented in Section 3) where no irreversible phenomena was considered. As the SWOT satellite has not been deployed yet, this algorithm is fed with simulated SWOT and Nadir altimetry observations based on a "nature run" of the NATL60 model (see Figure 3). This model is a ultra-high resolution simulator of the North Atlantic basin and provides a "pretend" real-world for the SWOT and Nadir simulators to obtain observations from. Then, the QG model is nudged by the BFN algorithm based on the synthetic observations provided by the satellite simulators. Finally, the BFN technique is benchmarked by comparison to the DUACS products and the nature run of NATL60.

As seen in black, in Figure 3, until now the observations have been taken as perfect, i.e. no measurement noise and errors have been taken into account. Hence, the objective of this research project is to build upon the work of Le Guillou et al. 2020 by implementing the BFN algorithm using realistic SWOT observations (both noisy and de-noised) and analyzing its performance. The goal is to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of observation noise in the BFN performance?

Figure 3: Flow chart of how data is used to test the current approach. It entails a NATL60 model, simulators of SWOT and Nadir altimetry data and a QG model nudged via the BFN technique. In black, the work of Le Guillou et al. 2020 and, in red, the added steps of this work.

2. What is the sensitivity of the BFN algorithm to different nudging strategies (under noisy observations)?
3. What is the effect of the de-noised observations in the BFN performance?
4. What is the sensitivity of the BFN algorithm to different nudging strategies (under de-noised observations)?

The above research questions are answered for two different regions of the North Atlantic basin which will be detailed in the next section.

4.1 Regions and the different effects of noise

The two regions under scope are the same as in Le Guillou et al. 2020 namely, a region containing a part of the Gulf Stream and a region on the Porcupine Abyssal plain, which are from now on referred to as GULFSTREAM and OSMOSIS, respectively.

The reasons behind experimenting on two regions are that these present different dynamics and are characterized by different temporal samplings of SWOT. Hence, the robustness of the BFN method can be shown. Additionally, the SWOT measurement noise will affect these regions to a different extent and the performance of the BFN will thus be region dependent. Further details on the regions can be found in Le Guillou et al. 2020.

As mentioned, the two regions are under different dynamical regimes: the GULFSTREAM is dominated by energetic mesoscale dynamics whereas the OSMOSIS region is less energetic, with small-scale processes that are more perceptible. Since the SWOT observations are infected by small-scale noise their effects will differ between the regions. Figures 4 and 5 show an example of the effect of noise on a SWOT observation for each region. The SWOT pass on the left is the perfect observation as used in the work of Le Guillou et al. 2020 and the one in the center is the observation contaminated by all errors and noise presented in Section 2.4.

As can be seen from Figures 4 and 5, the effect of noise in the GULFSTREAM region is almost imperceptible given that the dynamics of the region are much stronger than the noise. On the other hand, it is clear that for the OSMOSIS region the noise affects the observations to a much greater extent given the less energetic nature of its dynamics.

Additionally, Figures 4 and 5 show a third image (on the right) of the same pass after being de-noised using the method developed by Gómez-Navarro et al. 2020. Note that

Figure 4: GULFSTREAM Region: Examples of SWOT simulator output of SSH (m) for pass 93 of cycle 01 of the satellite’s orbit and considering a space-time sampling typical of the Science Phase of the mission. From left to right: the perfect observation, the realistic observation (with noise) and the observation after being filtered for KaRIn noise. Note the amplitude of measurements of SSH on the right.

Figure 5: OSMOSIS Region: Same as figure 4 but over the OSMOSIS Region. Example of simulator’s pass 07 of cycle 01 of the satellite’s orbit. Note the amplitude of measurements of SSH on the right.

the de-noising operation only filters the random noise present in the observations. In this work, the de-noising algorithm was used with the specific parameter $\lambda_2 = 20$ for the GULFSTREAM and $\lambda_2 = 30$ for the OSMOSIS region. Inspection of Figures 4 and 5 shows that the de-noising seems successful in removing the small-scale random noise thus, providing the possibility of implementing the BFN with these de-noised observations.

4.2 Diagnostics for Evaluation

Two evaluation diagnostics are considered which provide metrics on the algorithm’s performance.

Root Mean Square Error: The RMSE is computed as a function of time defined by:

$$RMSE(t) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (SSH(t, i) - SSH^{true}(t, i))^2} \tag{8}$$

where $SSH(t, i)$ and $SSH^{true}(t, i)$ are the values of the reconstructed field and the true field at grid point i and time t , N is the number of grid points within the study domain. For this diagnostic, the relative score $RMSE_S$ is defined as:

$$RMSE_S(t) = 1 - \frac{RMSE(t)}{RMS(SSH^{true})} \quad (9)$$

where RMS is the root mean square function. For a given time point, a score of 1 indicates a perfect reconstruction in terms of $RMSE$ while a score of zero indicates that the $RMSE$ is as large as the RMS of the true field. For this work a single scalar time-mean score of $RMSE_S$, referred to as RMSE score, is also computed and is used to compare the performances of different experiments. The closer to 1 the RMSE score, the more reliable the reconstructed field is.

Wavenumber Power Spectral Density: WPSD provides a spatial-scale dependent metric which is useful to identify the smallest scales resolved by the maps. This metric is computed as in Le Guillou et al. 2020 and in this work the score $WPSD_S$ is presented as a function of wavenumber, and defined by:

$$WPSD_S = 1 - \frac{WPSD(SSH - SSH^{true})}{WPSD(SSH^{true})} \quad (10)$$

Like the RMSE score, for a given wavenumber a score of 1 indicates a perfect reconstruction (the amplitude and phase of the corresponding harmonic is correct) and a score of 0 indicates no phase correlation. For the present work, the effective resolution (ER) of a reconstruction is used for comparison of experiments and is defined by the spatial scale at which $WPSD_S$ is equal to 0.5 (Ballarotta et al. 2019). Like the RMSE score it is also a single scalar. The effective resolution is expressed in kilometers and characterizes the spatial resolution of the reconstructed maps.

5 Results and Discussion

In order to answer the research questions proposed in Section 4 several experiments were made. The results for the OSMOSIS region are presented in Table 1 and for the GULF-STREAM region in Table 2. The results discussed in the following paragraphs will mainly relate to the SSH variable given its importance in the context of oceanography. Nevertheless, the results presented in the tables include the three variables: SSH, Velocity and RV.

The results for the OSMOSIS region (Table 1) show an expected outcome: adding the noisy SWOT observations to the Nadirs already in place degrades the reconstruction of all fields independently of the nudging strategy. Then, when the de-noised SWOT observations are added to the Nadirs the reconstructed fields improve from the Nadirs only scenario. The SSH field is enhanced by 10.2 km in ER while maintaining the RMSE score. Furthermore, this field differs from the best case scenario (i.e. using perfect SWOT observations) by 12.8 km in ER and by 0.06 in RMSE score. A comparison of the diagnostics for the different satellite scenarios and variables is illustrated in Figure 6 and Figure 7 in appendix A.

The performance improvement using the de-noised SWOT measurements is only seen for the relative vorticity (RV) nudging strategy. This is expected given that the spatially correlated errors still infect the observations making the vortex stretching term noisy. The effective resolution of the reconstructed SSH field is 60 km with an RMSE score of 0.81. This result confirms that the RV term can be used within a DA method to mitigate the

Table 1: OSMOSIS Region. Overview of results for the OSMOSIS region. Comparison between performance of nudging strategies (VS, RV, PV) under different observation regimes. The RMSE Score and the Effective Resolution are shown for the reconstructed fields of SSH, Velocity (Vel) and relative vorticity (RV).

Satellites	Nudging Strategy	RMSE score			Effective Resolution		
		SSH	Vel	RV	SSH	Vel	RV
Nadirs	VS	0.81	0.28	0.08	70.2	66.2	74.5
Nadirs + SWOT	PV	0.87	0.44	0.16	47.2	43.8	47.7
Nadirs + SWOT (with Noise)	VS	0.4	-0.09	-0.06	214.2	0	201.2
	RV	0.57	-0.18	-0.32	123.4	0	252.9
	PV	0.4	-0.12	-0.27	215.5	0	203.3
Nadirs + SWOT (De-noised)	VS	0.4	-0.08	-0.05	212.8	0	206.9
	RV	0.81	0.32	0.1	60	59.9	62.6
	PV	0.41	-0.06	-0.04	211.3	0	211

effect of spatially correlated errors. Additionally, the poor performance of the potential vorticity (PV) nudging strategy suggests that the nudging of the VS term is too strong and/or of the RV term is too weak. Future improvements on the BFN performance using this strategy could be achieved by readjusting the nudging strengths. Additionally, these results indicate that it is essential to de-noise observations in regions with low signal-to-noise ratio.

For the GULFSTREAM region, the results show that the SWOT measurement noise and errors have a small effect on the performance of the BFN across all nudging strategies. In fact, adding the noisy SWOT observations to the Nadirs only scenario slightly improves the reconstruction of the fields. For the SSH field an enhancement of 5.6 km in ER and a drop of 0.01 in RMSE score are seen for the best strategy of nudging RV. However, the noisy SWOT observations do degrade the fields when compared to the best case scenario of Nadirs and perfect SWOT observations. For the SSH field, a difference of 12.3 km in ER and of 0.04 in RMSE score arises. This indicates that for very dynamic regions the signal-to-noise ratio of SWOT is high enough such that it enables the BFN algorithm to still have a relatively good performance.

Under de-noised SWOT observations, the BFN performance is comparable to the noisy experiment for all strategies, where the RV strategy stands out. For this strategy, the reconstructed SSH field gains about 6 km in ER when compared with other strategies for a RMSE score of 0.86. Under the RV strategy, the reconstructed SSH field has an improvement of 11.5 km in ER and 0.01 in RMSE score from the Nadirs only scenario. Additionally, it differs by 6.4 km in ER and 0.02 in RMSE from the best case scenario. The SSH field is reconstructed with an ER of 89.9 km with RMSE score of 0.86. These results show that the random noise from the observations does not affect the VS term since, when de-noised, the performance of the BFN is similar for corresponding strategies.

Table 2: GULFSTREAM Region. Same overview of results as Table 1 but for the GULFSTREAM region.

Satellites	Nudging	RMSE score			Effective Resolution		
	Strategy	SSH	Vel	RV	SSH	Vel	RV
Nadirs	VS	0.85	0.48	0.09	101.4	85.2	108.5
Nadirs + SWOT	PV	0.88	0.56	0.13	83.5	71.2	89.2
Nadirs + SWOT	VS	0.84	0.48	0.06	96.1	78.3	104
	RV	0.84	0.46	-0.05	103.2	81.5	109.6
	(with Noise)	PV	0.84	0.48	-0.02	95.8	78.1
Nadirs + SWOT	VS	0.84	0.48	0.06	95.6	78.7	103.7
	RV	0.86	0.52	0.11	89.9	75.8	98.1
	(De-noised)	PV	0.84	0.49	0.07	95.2	77.9

Additionally, as for the OSMOSIS region, the nudging of the PV could be adjusted to give more importance to the RV term and improve the performance of BFN under such strategy.

6 Conclusion

For the less energetic OSMOSIS region, adding noisy SWOT observations to the Nadirs degrades the BFN performance to such extent that it becomes ineffectual. For the realistic case of de-noised SWOT observations, an improvement of 10.2 km in ER while maintaining the RMSE score is seen for the reconstructed SSH field. The effective resolution of this field is 60 km with an RMSE score of 0.81. This improvement occurs for the relative vorticity (RV) nudging strategy. Furthermore, the poor results of the potential vorticity (PV) nudging strategy indicate that the nudging coefficients should be balanced such that the weight of the RV term is higher in the nudging operation. Finally, these findings indicate that de-noising SWOT observations is critical in regions with low signal-to-noise ratio.

For the energetic GULFSTREAM region, adding noisy SWOT observations to the Nadirs affects the performance of the BFN to a much smaller extent. In fact, when compared to the Nadirs only scenario this improves the reconstruction of the SSH field by 5.4 km in ER whereas the RMSE scores drops by 0.01. Under de-noised SWOT observations the performance is still comparable to the noisy situation for all strategies, where again the RV strategy yields better results. The resulting SSH field has 89.9 km in ER and a RMSE score of 0.86. This translates into an increase by 11.5 km in ER and by 0.01 in RMSE score when compared to the Nadirs only scenario; and a decrease by 6.4 km in ER and 0.02 in RMSE score when compared to the best case scenario. For this region as well, the poor performance under the PV strategy indicates that the role of the RV term

in the nudging operation should be of higher importance.

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A Diagnostics

Figure 6: Comparison of BFN performance between the best nudging strategies of the Nadirs only, SWOT+Nadirs with noise and SWOT+Nadirs de-noised regimes. Plots show the time evolution of RMSE and RMSE-based score as well as the WPSD and WPSD based Score as a function of wavenumber. From top to bottom reconstructed fields of: SSH, Velocity (Vel) and Relative Vorticity (RV).

Figure 7: Same as Figure 6 but for the SWOT+Nadirs with perfect observations, SWOT+Nadirs with noise and SWOT+Nadirs de-noised regimes.

Figure 8: Same as Figure 6 but for the GULFSTREAM Region.

Figure 9: Same as Figure 7 but for the GULFSTREAM Region.